

Bromination of cholest-4-en-3,6-dione with *N*-bromosuccinimide in chloroform

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Abstract : The reaction of cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1) with *N*-bromosuccinimide in chloroform furnishes four compounds which have been identified as 2,7 α -dibromo-cholest-1,4-dien-3,6-dione (2), 2,2,7 α -tribromo-cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (3), 2 α ,7 α -dibromo-cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (4) and 2,2-dibromo-7-hydroxyl cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (5) by spectroscopic analyses.

Keywords : *N*-Bromosuccinimide, bromo derivative, 3,6-diketo steroid.

Introduction

In our previous communications we have reported the reactions of *N*-bromosuccinimide in dimethyl sulphoxide on various functionalities viz. (a) olefinic double bonds in steroid and triterpenoid skeletons¹⁻⁴, (b) kelo functional group of 3-keto triterpenoid with or without hydrogen at C-4⁵⁻⁷ and (c) keto oximes of 3-keto-triterpenoids⁸. This time we have investigated the reaction of *N*-bromosuccinimide on a diketone taking cholest-4-en-3,6-dione as a model compound in chloroform at elevated temperature to unveil the nature of the products formed in a rapid reaction.

Results and discussion

In a solution of cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1; 1.4 g, 3.51 mmol) in chloroform. NBS (2.1 g, 11.79 mmol) was added in small portions at a time and then refluxed for 2 h on water bath and then worked up in the usual way. The product obtained was chromatographed over neutral silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether (PE)-ethyl acetate (EA) (99 : 1), PE-EA (98 : 2), PE-EA (96 : 4) and PE-EA (95 : 5) furnished four compounds 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively.

The compound 2 purified by repeated crystallizations from CHCl₃-MeOH that was analyzed for C₂₇H₃₈Br₂O₂ had the m.p. 200–202 °C. The IR spectrum showed absorption at 1660 cm⁻¹ and UV showed absorption at 259 nm indicating the presence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl function and the bathochromic shift (1 shows absorption

at 250 nm) indicated that one of the bromine atoms is attached to the olefinic double bond of the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group^{9,10}. Its MS showed triplet molecular ion peak at *m/z* 556, 554, 552 in the ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 [M⁺] indicating the presence of two bromine atoms in 2; the other fragments appeared at *m/z* 476, 474 (1 : 1) [M⁺-HBr], 447, 445, 395, 361, 247, 233, 230, 215 (base), 213, 133.57 (96%) and 55 (98%). The ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2 showed five methyl groups of which two appeared as singlets at δ 0.77 and 1.24 and three appeared as doublets at δ 0.86, 0.87 and 0.93 (*J* 6.5 Hz each). The doublet centered at δ 4.41 integrating for one proton with a small coupling constant of *J* 3.5 Hz indicated that one of the bromine atoms is axially attached to the C-7 carbon atom, the β -equatorial H-7 coupling with β -axial C-8 proton; the singlet at δ 6.57 ppm integrating for one proton was assigned to H-4 proton and the downfield one proton singlet at δ 7.45 ppm was due to olefinic H-1. The ¹³C NMR accounted for all 27 carbons. The compound 2 exhibited singlets downfield at δ_c 177.5 ppm and 194.0 ppm due to C-3 and C-6 carbonyl groups respectively. The singlet at δ_c 124.6 ppm and doublet at 152.8 ppm were assigned to carbon-carbon double bonds of the enone moiety. From the above spectral data the compound 2 has been assigned as 2,7 α -dibromocholest-1,4-dien-3,6-dione. It is noteworthy to state that the substitution at the C-2 by a bromine atom causes an up field shielding effect on the ¹³C NMR of the

carbonyl carbon at C-3 position by about 8.5 ppm (Table 1) corroborating our earlier observation on triterpenoid ketones¹⁰.

Table 1. Comparison of C-13 chemical shifts (ppm) of **2**, **3**, **4** and **5** with those of cholest-4-en-3-one (**A**), androst-1,4-dien-3,17-dione (**B**) and starting compound (**1**)

Carbon no.	A	B	1	2	3	4	5
1	35.7	155.2	35.5	152.7	59.9	49.2	59.6
2	33.9	127.6	33.9	124.6	57.0	47.5	54.4
3	198.9	186.0	199.4	177.5	184.0	190.4	184.0
4	123.6	124.0	125.4	127.1	122.9	126.6	123.5
5	171.0	168.2	161.0	157.9	159.0	159.3	156.4
6	32.9	32.3	202.3	194.0	194.0	194.0	187.0
7	32.1	31.2	46.8	41.9	42.4	42.2	75.4
8	35.2	35.0	34.2	35.6	37.4	37.7	50.1
9	53.8	52.3	51.0	51.9	51.9	51.9	50.7
10	38.6	43.4	39.1	48.3	45.7	43.8	44.0
11	21.0	22.0	20.9	22.0	20.5	20.4	21.3
12	39.4	32.5	39.8	39.4	38.4	38.3	38.8
13	42.4	47.6	42.5	42.4	43.4	43.4	42.6
14	56.0	50.4	56.0	55.6	55.6	55.6	55.2
15	24.1	21.8	24.0	23.7	23.8	23.7	25.9
16	28.1	35.5	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.0	28.2
17	56.1	219.6	56.5	57.6	57.6	57.6	56.1
18	12.0	13.8	11.9	12.4	12.4	12.3	12.9
19	17.4	18.7	17.5	19.2	18.5	18.4	18.4
20	35.7		35.7	35.6	35.6	35.6	35.7
21	18.7		18.6	18.6	18.6	18.6	18.8
22	36.1		36.0	35.9	36.0	36.0	36.0
23	23.8		23.8	23.7	22.8	23.7	23.8
24	39.6		39.4	39.4	39.4	39.4	39.4
25	27.9		28.0	27.8	27.8	27.8	28.0
26	22.5		22.5	22.5	22.5	22.5	22.5
27	22.8		22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8

Compound **3** melts at 192–194 °C, it was analyzed for $C_{27}H_{39}Br_3O_2$. The IR spectrum showed absorption at 1660 cm^{-1} and UV showed absorption peak at 249 nm indicating the presence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group. Its MS also showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 638, 636, 634, 632 in the ratio 1 : 3 : 3 : 1 indicating the presence of three bromine atoms in the compound. Other fragments appeared at m/z 558, 556, 554 (1 : 2 : 1) [$M^+ - HBr$], 476, 474 (1 : 1) [$M^+ - 2HBr$], 450, 448, 395, 370, 369, 321, 267, 247, 215, 161, 135, 57 (base). The structure of compound **3** was confirmed from its PMR spectrum that showed the presence of five methyls, three of

which appeared as doublets at δ 0.87, 0.89, 0.93 each one with same coupling constant of 6.5 Hz due to the three secondary methyls, and two as singlets at δ 0.76 and 1.47 ppm. The one proton doublet at δ 4.38 (J 3.5 Hz) was assigned to H-7 indicating that the bromine is α -axially oriented at C-7. The ^{13}C NMR signals showed singlets at 194.0 ppm and 184.0 ppm for two carbonyl groups and the downfield shift is due to the presence of two bromine atoms at C-2 and one bromine atom in C-7 position, C-4 and C-5 carbon atoms appeared at 122.9 ppm as doublet and 159.0 ppm as singlet respectively. The other ^{13}C NMR spectral features of **3** allowed its formulation as 2,2,7 α -tribromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione.

Compound **4** was analyzed for $C_{27}H_{40}Br_2O_2$, m.p. 165 °C; its IR spectrum showed absorption at 1657 cm^{-1} and UV absorption at 249 nm suggesting that the compound **4** also contained the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group. The MS showed the triplet molecular ion peak at m/z 558, 556, 554 in the ratio 1 : 2 : 1 indicating the presence of two bromine atoms in it. It was identified as 2 $\alpha,7\alpha$ -dibromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione from its MS, 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectral features.

Compound **5** was analyzed for $C_{27}H_{40}Br_2O_3$, m.p. 170–172 °C. The IR spectrum showed absorption peak for the ketonic group at a higher frequency 1710 cm^{-1} is due to the electronic repulsion of the equatorial bromine atom¹¹ at C-2 and broad band at $3200\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for hydroxyl group. The UV showed absorption at 249 nm indicating the presence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group. Its MS showed the triplet molecular ion peak at m/z 570, 572, 574 [M^+] in the ratio 1 : 2 : 1 indicating the presence of two bromine atoms in it. The compound was formulated as 2,2-dibromo-7-hydroxycholest-4-en-3,6-dione from its spectral data.

Structure of compounds **2**, **3**, **4** and **5** have also been confirmed by making a comparison of the ^{13}C NMR data (Table 1) of cholest-4-en-3-one (**A**), androst-1,4-dien-3-one (**B**) with those of the starting material cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (**1**).

CD spectra of compound **2**, **3** and **4** were also compared with that of the starting compound **1**. The compound **1** showed a maximum absorption at 225.2 ($\Delta\epsilon = 9.46$) nm and two troughs at 262.2 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.75$) nm and 344.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.43$) nm whereas compound **2** exhibited absorption maxima at 215 ($\Delta\epsilon = 9.46$) nm with valleys at 232.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = 1.6$) nm and 240 ($\Delta\epsilon = -0.95$) nm with minimum absorption at 245.2 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.71$) nm which was accompanied by another peak at 270.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = 5.12$)

nm and a minimum absorption at 348.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.26$) nm. Compound **3** exhibited a negative Cotton effect at 231.2 ($\Delta\epsilon = -6.08$) nm accompanied by a valley at 249.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = -3.63$) nm with maximum absorption at 318.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = 1.18$) nm and a second minimum absorption at 369.4 ($\Delta\epsilon = -0.96$) nm and compound **4** also showed a negative Cotton effect at 219.0 ($\Delta\epsilon = -3.05$) nm associated with a valley at 214.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = -2.66$) nm and the highest absorption peak at 258.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = 8.87$) nm preceded by a valley at 235.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = 4.35$) nm and a second minimum at the higher wave length at 351.4 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.02$) nm. From the above data it may be concluded that in the bromine atom at C-2 position in **4** is equatorially oriented below the plane of the ring that causes the change in the Cotton effect which is also observable in compound **3** as well whereas compound **2**, as expected, do not show such a change in Cotton effect due to the absence of a chiral centre at C-2 position. The sharp change in the pattern of CD curve in compound **3** indicates that the conformation of ring **A** is changed to some extent due to the presence

of additional bromine atom at C-2 position. Construction of Dreiding model shows that the bromine atom at C-7 position is oriented axially downwards the plane of the ring **B** in all the three compounds **2**, **3** and **4**. Thus the CD spectra of all the three compounds are in complete agreement with the assigned structures.

As is expected^{2,8} NBS in polar solvent acts as a source of bromonium ion and that electrophilic Br^+ attacks the C-2 position of the enol form of compound **1** to produce the bromo derivatives **3** and **4**. Introduction of one as well as two bromine atoms on the α carbon of a carbonyl group 3-keto triterpenoid skeleton in presence of NBS in polar solvent have already been reported⁵⁻⁷. The compound **2** may be formed by the simultaneous dehydrobromination of compound **3** in the polar solvent due to the sterical crowding and conformation of ring-A containing an olefinic double bond⁸. Hydrolysis of the Br at C-7 bond may result in the formation of small amount of C-7 hydroxy derivative^{2,12} **5** originating from **3** (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

Materials and method :

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum had b.p. 60–80 °C. PMR spectra (chemical shifts in δ , ppm; TMS as internal standard) and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 Bruker Avance 300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer, Bruker WH-400 and Bruker WH-270 with DEPT spectra respectively; IR spectra in nujol on Beckman IR-20 or Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr discs or Pye Unicem-300 spectrometer; UV spectra in *n*-hexane or methanol on Shimadzu UV-240 spectrometer; mass spectra in Varian MAT 711 instrument at 70 eV and CD spectra on a Jubin Yuon III instrument in *n*-hexane. All the chemicals were of reagent grade (from Merck, Fluka, SRL etc.) and were purified prior to their use following the standard protocols. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (BDH, 60–120 mesh). TLC was performed over silica gel G.

Reaction of cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1) with NBS in CHCl_3 :

Compound 1 (1.4 g, 3.51 mmol) was dissolved in CHCl_3 (30 ml) and then NBS (2.1 g, 11.79 mmol) added to it in small lots, the mixture was refluxed about 2 h and then cooled. It was extracted with CHCl_3 and then extract was washed several times with water, dried with Na_2SO_4 and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue (1.2 g) was chromatographed over silica gel (60 g). Elution furnished the following compounds : 2 [1.0 g, 9.4%, EA : PE (1 : 99)], 3 [0.4 g, 25.2%, EA : PE (2 : 98)], 4 [0.35 g, 26.3%, EA : PE (4 : 96)] and 5 [0.15 g, 11.6%, EA : PE (5 : 95)].

2,7 α -Dibromo-cholest-1,4-dien-3,6-dione (2) :

Compound 2 was crystallized from CHCl_3 -MeOH to afford white crystals, m.p. 200–202 °C; Beilstein test : positive; IR : 1660 cm^{-1} (C=C-CO-); UV : λ_{max} (*n*-hexane) 259 nm (ϵ 20000); CD : λ_{max} (*n*-hexane) 215 ($\Delta\epsilon = 9.46$), 232.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = 1.6$ valley), 240 ($\Delta\epsilon = -0.95$), 245.2 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.71$), 270.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = 5.12$) and 348.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.26$) nm; MS : m/z 556, 554, 552 (1 : 2 : 1) [M^+], 476, 474 (1 : 1) [M^+ -HBr], other fragments are 447, 445, 395, 361; 247, 233, 230, 215 (base), 213, 113, 107, 105, 95, 91, 83, 81, 71, 69, 67, 57 (96%), 55 (98%); ^1H NMR : δ 0.77, 1.24 (2 \times 3H, s, *tert*-Me), 0.86 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 0.87 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 0.93 (3H,

d, J 6.5 Hz) (3d, 3 \times *sec*-Me), 4.41 (d, J 3.5 Hz, H-7), 6.57 (s, H-4), 7.45 (s, H-1) ppm; ^{13}C NMR : 152.8 (C1), 124.6 (C2), 177.5 (C3 carbonyl carbon), 127.1 (C4), 157.9 (C5), 194.0 (C6 carbonyl carbon), 41.9 (C7) (Found : C, 58.30; H, 6.90; Br, 28.80. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{38}\text{Br}_2\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 58.49; H, 6.91; Br, 28.83%).

2,2,7 α -Tribromo-cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (3) :

Compound 3 was crystallized from CHCl_3 -MeOH to afford fine crystals, m.p. 192–194 °C; Beilstein test : positive; IR : 1660 cm^{-1} (>C=C-C=O); UV : λ_{max} (*n*-hexane) 249 nm (ϵ 18000); CD : λ_{max} (*n*-hexane) 231 ($\Delta\epsilon = -6.08$), 249.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = -3.63$ valley), 318.8 ($\Delta\epsilon = 1.18$), 369.4 ($\Delta\epsilon = -0.96$) nm; MS : m/z 638, 636, 634, 632 (1 : 3 : 3 : 1) [M^+], 558, 556, 554 (1 : 2 : 1) [M^+ -HBr], 476, 474 (1 : 1) [M^+ -2HBr], other fragments are 450, 448, 395, 370, 369, 368, 323, 321, 319, 269, 267, 265, 255, 247, 215, 213, 161, 160, 135, 133, 109, 107, 81, 79, 69, 57 (base); ^1H NMR : δ 0.76, 1.47 (2 \times 3H, s, *tert*-Me), 0.87 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 0.89 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 0.93 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz) (3d, 3 \times *sec*-Me), 3.28 (AB_q, J 16 Hz, 2H, C-1 methylene protons), 4.38 (1H, d, J_{ea} 3.5 Hz, H-7), 6.28 (s, H-4) ppm; ^{13}C NMR : 59.9 (C1), 57.0 (C2), 184.0 (C3 carbonyl carbon), 122.9 (C4), 159.0 (C5), 194.0 (C6 carbonyl carbon), 42.4 (C7) (Found : C, 50.91; H, 6.17; Br, 37.59. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{39}\text{Br}_3\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 51.04 ; H, 6.19; Br, 37.73%).

2 α ,7 α -Dibromo-cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (4) :

Compound 4 was crystallized from CHCl_3 -MeOH to furnish white crystals, m.p. 165 °C; Beilstein test : positive; IR : 1657 cm^{-1} ; UV : λ_{max} (*n*-hexane) : 249 nm (>C=C-C=O); CD : λ_{max} (*n*-hexane) 214.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = -2.66$, valley), 219 ($\Delta\epsilon = -3.05$), 235.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = 4.35$), 258.6 ($\Delta\epsilon = -8.87$), 351.4 ($\Delta\epsilon = -1.02$) nm; MS : m/z 558, 556, 554 (1 : 2 : 1) [M^+], 476, 474 (1 : 1) [M^+ -HBr], other fragments are 450, 449, 447, 398, 397, 395, 370, 363, 323, 321, 285, 249, 247, 215, 135, 69, 57 (83%), 55 (base); ^1H NMR : δ 0.77, 1.24 (2 \times 3H, s, *tert*-Me), 0.87 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 0.88 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), 0.94 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz), (3d, 3 \times *sec*-Me), 2.48 (1H, t, J 14 Hz), 2.71 (1H, dd, J 5 and 14 Hz), 4.86 (1H, dd, J 5 and 14 Hz), 4.39 (1H, d, J 3.5 Hz, H-7), 6.34 (1H, s, H-4) ppm; ^{13}C NMR : 49.2 (C1), 47.5 (C2), 190.4 (C3 carbonyl carbon), 126.6 (C4), 159.3 (C5), 194.0 (C6 carbonyl carbon), 42.3 (C7) (Found : C, 58.21; H, 7.23;

Br, 28.74. $C_{27}H_{40}Br_2O_2$ requires : C, 58.28; H, 7.25; Br, 20.72%).

2,2-Dibromo-7-hydroxycholest-4-en-3,6-dione (5) :

Compound **5** was crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH to afford white crystals, m.p. 170–172 °C; Beilstein test : positive; IR : 1710 cm^{-1} , $3200\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$; UV : λ_{max} (*n*-hexane) 249 nm; MS : *m/z* : 570, 572, 574 (1 : 2 : 1) [M^+], 555 [M^+ -OH], 475 [$(M^+$ -OH)-Br], other fragments are 413, 377, 323, 301, 279, 226, 149 (base); 1H NMR : δ 0.81, 1.39 ($2 \times 3H$, s, *tert*-Me), 0.86 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz), 0.88 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz), 0.93 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz) (3d, $3 \times$ *tert*-Me), 3.21 (2H, s, C1 methylene protons appeared as a broad), 6.42 (1H, s, olefinic proton at C-4), 2.01 (multiplet), 2.39 (t, *J* 9.45 Hz); ^{13}C NMR : 59.6 (C1), 54.4 (C2), 184.0 (C3 carbonyl carbon), 123.5 (C4), 156.4 (C5), 187.0 (C6 carbonyl carbon), 75.4 (C7).

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